

Mansoor, Hasan (2007). **Arab Media on the Internet: An Analytical-Evaluative Study for a Sample of the Arab Media Websites on the Internet (Doctoral dissertation, Al-Azhar University, Egypt).**

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Abstract:

This study has tried to examine how the Arabic mass media (including newspapers, magazines, radio stations and TV channels) make use of technology benefits and interactive services provided by the worldwide web, and the level to which these websites provide the elements of the content which promote media organization, using analytical, evaluative methods as a necessary start for developing insights and reasonable solutions for the defects in internet services provided by such media through its websites.

Study Sections:

This study is comprised of two basic parts, one of which is a theoretical and the other is a practical, including seven sections and a conclusion as follows:

Part 1: Study Theoretical Frame.

It constitutes of 4 chapters:

Chapter 1: Research Problem & Methodology.

Chapter 2: Internet studies. Theoretical Introductions and Assessment Criteria.

Chapter 3: Online Media—International Models.

Chapter 4: Online Arabic Media – Origin & Development.

Part 2: Study Practical Frame.

It constitutes of 3 chapters:

Chapter 5: Methodical Procedures of the Analytical Study.

Chapter 6: Analytical Study Results

Chapter 7: Study Hypotheses Testing

Conclusion: including the Research Abstract, Discussions and Recommendations.

Study Methodology:

The study has based upon the methodology of survey (by samples), since the comprehensive survey of all websites related to the Arabic media on the internet is found to be extremely difficult. The comparative methodology has been used to make comparisons between various Arabic Mass Media (TV channels, radio stations and the press) on the basis of how each of them make use of the massive capabilities provided by the Internet in the field of media services, and also, the historical methodology has been used to trace the origin, rise and development of the Arabic and international websites on the Worldwide web.

Research Sample:

The study is based upon a variety of internet research engines, in order to get a sample represents internet websites related to various Arabic Mass Media (including newspapers, magazines, radio stations and TV channels). The analysis sample included (122) websites, and it is a selected sample represented in the websites of the Arabic Mass Media, which are included in the list of The Most Popular 100.000 Sites on the web, according ALEXA statistics.

Research Time Domain:

As for the sample analysis time, it took nine months, passing through three stages:

Stage 1: During (September 2005) a survey has been conducted over 344 sites related to Arabic Mass Media, through search engines, and it has been limited to (122) sites, for they were the most important in ALEXA statistics.

Stage 2: During (December 2005) an analytical study was conducted and some evaluative criteria (related to the study) were applied so as to know how the Arabic Mass Media, through its sites, make use of technological benefits and interactive services provided the internet, and the extent to which these sites provide the content elements which promote media organizations.

Stage 3: During (June 2006), the Analytical Study criteria have been applied to the sites, study sample, for the second time, so as to know the level of growth or retreat occurred in the (efficiency and interactivity) criterion and the criterion of (media organization promotion).

Analysis Tool:

Through the study, the tool of (content analysis) has been used. In addition, the study has designed two (quantitative criteria), the first of which aims at measuring the level of the (efficiency and interactivity) of construction elements in the home pages of the Arabic Mass Media Websites and constitutes of 100 points, and the other measures the level of media organisation promotion through their and constitutes of 100 points as well.

Conclusions:

- The results showed the websites, study sample, succeeded in presenting the media organisation promotion more than in making use of the technological benefits and interactive services provided by the Internet (efficiency and interactivity), since the sites, as a whole, failed to get an average degree equals at least 50% of the (efficiency and interactivity) criterion points, which constitutes of 100 points. The site which scored the first was (Al-Jazeera Net), scoring (77 points), then followed by the Lebanese site of (Al-Nahar) and (Mont Carlo radio) site, then followed by the Egyptian site of (Al-Akhbar), then the (Emirate Foundation for Information), then the Saudi site of (Okaz), and then (Oman Radio Net) site.

As for the criterion of media organisation promotion through websites, the study related sites scored 64 points out of 100 points, and 79.5% of the sites scored more than 50 points according to the criterion. The sites of Aljazeera.net and al-Arabiya.net and the Lebanese annahar.com were the best in media organisation promotion, scoring up to 95% according to the criterion.

- The websites, of the study sample, scored a slight growth in the criteria of (efficiency and interactivity) and (media organisation promotion) after 6 months of the first stage of analysis. However, the growth was clearer in the first criterion, since the difference between the two has statistical significance in both the efficiency and interactivity criteria between the average degree scored by the sites in December 2005 and June 2006, but it has no statistical significance in the second criterion, except in one sub-criterion of (forms of content).

The Hypotheses Tests:

- 1- The study results have accepted the first hypothesis. It refers to the existence of differences having statistical significance between the level of providing technological benefits and interactive services (efficiency and interactivity) in the intended sites, and the level of providing the elements of (media organisation promotion). The test result

of this hypothesis means that the sites, of the study sample, succeeded in presenting itself as extensions of the traditional mass media, more than in succeeding as online sites providing information service and make use of the web benefits, especially the interactivity benefit.

- 2- Results have referred to the existence of differences having statistical significance in the levels of providing technological benefits and interactive services between the study sites. Only the scores of (magazines' sites) showed the existence of differences having statistical significance between them and the scores of other sites, that means the magazines' sites were (the source of variation).
- 3- Results have found that the third hypothesis is rejected. It refers to the existence of differences having statistical significance in the degrees of the (total criterion) of providing the elements of media organisation promotion on the websites.
- 4- Results proved that the fourth hypothesis is partially accepted, since the variable of (media types) has affected the degrees of online sites in a number of efficiency and interactivity criteria. The differences between the degrees of sites had statistical significance in the criteria of (complexity of choice available, and immediacy). The magazines' sites were the source of variation in both criteria.
- 5- Results have accepted the fifth hypothesis. it says that the type of medium has affected the degrees of the media organisation promotion criteria, and that the sites degrees varies according to the media published by it in the four criteria, the magazines' sites were the source of variation in the criterion of the forms of content, the (TV) sites were the source of variation in the criterion of the period of media archive, and the (radio) sites were the source of variation in the criterion of subscription and advertisement details.
- 6- The results have found that the sixth hypothesis is rejected. It says that the media sizes (whether it is local, regional or international) affects the scores of the criterion of efficiency and interactivity of the websites published by such media. However, the results proved that there are difference having statistical significance between the sites published by major media organizations and the other sites in the gross criterion of efficiency and interactivity. The differences were clearer in the criterion of (complexity of choice available)
- 7- The results proved that the eighth hypothesis is partially accepted, and referred that the media ownership variable (government vs private media) affects the scores of its websites in two criteria of efficiency and interactivity; The criterion of complexity of choice available and the criterion of immediacy.
- 8- The results have found that the last hypothesis is rejected. It says that the media ownership variable (government vs private media) affects the scores of its websites in the criterion of media organisation promotion through its website, which means that the websites, study sample, haven't shown differences having statistical significance in this criterion.